

Transferable Skills Development through Project-Based Learning in an Industrial Engineering and Management Degree

Violeta Carvalho^{1,2,3,4}, Cristina S. Rodrigues¹, Senhorinha Teixeira¹, Ângela Silva¹, Rui M. Sousa¹, Lino Costa¹, Anabela Alves¹, Carina Pimentel¹

¹ ALGORITMI/LASI Research Center, School of Engineering, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

² Mechanical Engineering and Resource Sustainability Center (MEtRICS), University of Minho, Campus de Azurém, Guimarães, Portugal

³ Center for MicroElectromechanical Systems (CMEMS UMinho), University of Minho, Campus de Azurém, Guimarães, Portugal

⁴ LABBELS—Associate Laboratory, 4806-909 Braga/Guimarães, Portugal

Email: violeta.carvalho@dps.uminho.pt, crodrigues@dps.uminho.pt, st@dps.uminho.pt, asilva@dps.uminho.pt, rms@dps.uminho.pt, lac@dps.uminho.pt, anabela@dps.uminho.pt, carina.pimentel@dps.uminho.pt

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14062853>

Abstract

In the literature, transferable skills refer to the ability to learn and apply knowledge, skills, and attitudes in various professional contexts to solve real-world problems, always taking ethical values into account. Due to job market demands, it becomes imperative to promote these skills in Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) students, and the active learning strategy Project-Based Learning (PBL) is an excellent opportunity to do so. Since 2004/05, the Department of Production and Systems (DPS) of the Engineering School, University of Minho (UM), Portugal, has been implementing PBL with students of the IEM Degree. In each of the three years of this degree, there is a semester-long Curricular Unit (CU) of PBL integrated project in IEM, namely IPIEM I, IPIEM II, and IPIEM III. Each of these projects involves the other CU of the respective semester. The main purpose of this paper is, based on a published framework of 23 transferable skills, to identify the extent to which each of these projects promotes the development of these skills, thus detecting strengths and weaknesses, and proposing possible improvement actions. It also aims to verify whether there is an evolution in the development of some of these skills throughout the IEM Degree. This exploratory study provides valuable teacher-centric insights, highlighting the need for incorporating student perspectives to enrich the understanding of PBL's impact on the educational process.

Keywords: Industrial Engineering and Management; Active Learning; Project-Based Learning; Transferable Skills.

1 Introduction

Transferable skills, i.e. the abilities adaptable across various tasks and contexts, form the foundation of professional capability. These skills, including communication, problem-solving, and teamwork, empower individuals to overcome challenges, collaborate effectively, and succeed in diverse environments (Pinto et al., 2023).

In the scope of the Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM) area, where multidisciplinary approaches and problem-solving are central, the development of these skills is particularly vital for success both during higher education and in future careers. They are not typically taught in a traditional classroom setting but are developed through experiences such as extracurricular activities, internships, part-time jobs, interactions with peers and mentors, as well as through active learning methodologies. The latter prioritizes student engagement, participation, and application of knowledge, fostering a deeper understanding of concepts and better retention of skills (Blinkoff et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2024). By integrating active learning strategies into the educational context, institutions aim to equip students not only with technical know-how but also with the versatile skill set necessary for success in the dynamic field of industrial engineering (Balalle, 2024; Kalu et al., 2023; Quibrantar & Ezezika, 2023).

This type of methodologies, such as problem-based learning, project-based learning (PBL), collaborative learning, and experiential learning, provide students with opportunities to develop and refine transferrable skills in real contexts. For instance, in problem-based learning scenarios, students are tasked with solving real-world engineering problems, requiring them to apply critical thinking, creativity, and teamwork to develop viable solutions (Dunmoye et al., 2024; Navío-Marco et al., 2024). Similarly, PBL assignments challenge students to manage projects from conception to completion, enhancing their time management, communication, and leadership abilities along the way. By actively engaging in these learning experiences, students not only deepen their understanding of theoretical concepts but also develop the transferrable skills necessary for success in professional life. Moreover, the interactive nature of active learning methodologies promotes collaboration, communication, and adaptability, skills that are highly valued in engineering practice. As a result, the integration of active learning approaches into higher education curricula not only enhances academic outcomes but also prepares students to surpass the complexities of the IEM area by equipping them with a robust toolkit of transferrable skills (Chatpinyakoo et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2024). For instance, Zen et al. (Zen et al., 2022) explored the impact of Project-Based Online Learning (PBOL) and student engagement on academic achievement in higher education, with a focus on preparing graduates for the job market. The results suggested that PBOL and student engagement positively influence academic performance while entrepreneurship was fostered by having entrepreneurship lecturers. Marnewick et al. (Marnewick, 2023) identified several transferrable skills (analytical/critical thinking, communication, problem-solving, time management, teamwork, and project management) after a PBL implemented at a South African university. Similarly, Cicmil and co-workers (Cicmil et al., 2006) identified critical thinking, self-management of time, adaptability; problem-solving, communication skills, and interpersonal skills.

PBL methodologies have been implemented since 2004 in IEM programmes of the Department of Production and Systems (DPS) of the Engineering School, University of Minho (UM), Portugal, where transferable skills are inherent (Lima et al., 2007). The primary objective of this research is to analyse the progressive development of transferable skills in the IEM Degree students as they experience the three PBL projects offered throughout the course. Firstly, the three project CU are described. Then, based on the literature, the set of transferable skills is presented. Finally, using the previous information and the teachers' perceptions (mainly), the level at which these skills are considered in each project is assessed. The results include the identification of aspects to be improved in each of the projects, the proposal of concrete actions in this regard, and the finding that there are transferable skills that are improved throughout the three projects.

2 Study Context

Since the academic year of 2021/2022, a new study plan was implemented in the IEM Degree at DPS-UM. This new plan incorporates three semestrial Curricular Units (CU), one per year, entitled Integrated Project in IEM I, II, and III (IPIEM I, IPIEM II, and IPIEM III), as they integrate, as Project Supporting Courses (PSC), the remaining UC of the respective semester. In fact, the adoption of PBL at DPS, UM dates to 2004, when the first edition of an IPIEM was held, even without being included in the course's curricular structure.

The main teaching objectives of these IPIEM CU can be summarised as:

- Development of technical skills by applying the syllabus contents of the PSC in the context of the project.
- Development of transversal skills in a team-based environment.

The main aim of this initiative was also to provide students with a learning environment that encourages investigation, critical thinking, teamwork, problem-solving skills, and hands-on activities. Furthermore, the

execution of the projects poses several challenges to students in terms of project management, task planning, meeting deadlines, communication, and teamwork.

2.1 IPIEM I

The IPIEM I is included in the IEM program of the first semester, first year. The semester has six CU, each holding five European Credit Transfer System (ECTS) (1 ECTS means 28 hours of student work) (Figure 1). All CU contribute as PSC for the project development using PBL approach. PSC of Engineering School are four: Computer Programming I (CP I), Integrated Project on Industrial Engineering and Management I (IPIEM I), Introduction to Economics Engineering (IEE) and Introduction to Industrial Engineering and Management (IEM). The PSC from the Sciences School are Calculus for Engineering (CE) and Linear Algebra for Engineering (LA). This means the first year includes Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) CU that must be integrated in an interdisciplinary project to solve the challenge provided (Alves et al., 2019).

Regime	Curricular Unit	ECTS
Year 1		60
S1	Calculus for Engineering	5
S1	Computer Programming I	5
S1	Integrated Project in Industrial Engineering and Management I	5
S1	Introduction to Economics Engineering	5
S1	Introduction to Industrial Engineering and Management	5
S1	Linear Algebra for Engineering	5

Figure 1. Curricular units of first year, first semester of IEM Degree (adapted from UMinho (UMinho, 2023))

IPIEM I project theme have been always focused on sustainability issues (Alves, Moreira, et al., 2017; Colombo et al., 2014, 2015; Moreira et al., 2011). The 2023-24 edition was no exception, addressing the design of a production system for sorting, remanufacturing, revalorising and/or recycling end-of-life electric scooters, including all the aspects related to the development of the new products.

The IPIEM I project involved teachers from different courses, voluntary tutors (department lecturers and third-year IEM Degree students) and, sometimes, voluntary educational researchers in a total of 21 team members to manage this edition. The project is regularly developed in the first semester, i.e. from September to January. Team coordinator first step is to have a meeting, before classes starting (first week of September) to define the project management (time, resources, theme and so on). More details are provided in Alves et al. (2021).

In the first week of classes (11 to 16 of September), the project is presented to freshman students, which arrived at university one week before, in a session organized by the coordination team. The presentation has the following points: (i) Framework; (ii) History of PBL projects, motivation, and some alumni testimonials; (iii) Coordination team; (iv) Learning project guide including tutors' role, milestones and deliverables, assessment methodology, project theme, presentation of the pilot project, plan, and schedule first and second week, operation and use of project rooms and, finally; (v) Formation of teams and assignment of tutors. The learning project guide is a word document prepared by the coordination team for students to read and follow, explaining all details of PBL process organization, coordination team contacts, learning outcomes expected from each course, time schedules, tutors' role, among others important elements (Alves et al., 2021). In this edition, 68 freshman students were organized in eight teams of eight to nine members.

In the courses regular classes, it was better explained what student teams should do (project related tasks) to contribute for the project development in IPIEM I. Each course defines the tasks and its contents, but the idea is to integrate all or almost all contents in the project development (Alves et al., 2019). With this project, students must develop not only technical but also transversal competencies.

IPIEM I assessment included some deliverables that were presented in specific milestones (M) during the semester, as illustrated in Table 1. This is a time-consuming task for coordination team; however, it is important

to have assessment *for* and *as* learning through the project development (Fernandes et al., 2012, 2021). The team assessment counts for 90% and the remaining 10% comes from a triad challenge, named IEM@ProjectNetworking (Alves et al., 2013, 2022).

Table 1. IPIEM I milestones, deliverables, and weight of each in the assessment methodology.

M	Date	Deliverables	Weight
1	2023.09.20 (Week 2)	09h10 – 12h00: Pilot-project presentation (10'/team + 5' discussion)	Not assessed
2	2023.10.18 (Week 6)	09h10 – 12h00: Team progress (10'/team) + enlarged tutorial (15'/team).	7,5% (team) + not assessed
3	2023.11.14 (Week 9)	09h10 – 13h00: IEM@ProjectNetworking result (5'/pair)	10% (triad)
4	2023.12.01 (Week 12)	18h00 – Preliminary report (30 pages maximum).	25% (team)
5	2024.01.03 (Week 14)	18h00 – Final report (40 pages maximum)	40% (team)
6	2024.01.08 (Week 15)	09h00 – 17h00: Final presentation and discussion (15'/team+ 30' discussion) + blog + Padlet	12,5% + 7.5% + 7.5% (team)

2.2 IPIEM II

The implementation of the Integrated Project of the 2nd year of the IEM Degree took place for the first time, in the academic year of 2021/2022, and comprises four different CU of the 4th semester. These are Complements of Applied Statistics (5 ECTS), Operational Research and Optimization (5 ECTS), Numerical Methods (5 ECTS), and Information Systems and Technology (5 ECTS). The coordination team includes the project coordinator the teachers involved in the four CU. The technical skills given by these four subjects dictates the project main characteristic of challenging students to deal with real data, requiring learning skills from the CU involved: applying statistical data analysis techniques, database manipulation and management tools, and implementing software solutions related to data processing/analysis.

For this project, the students are organised in teams of 8 to 10 members. Along the three years of project implementation, the engineering problem proposed to the teams have been changing. In its first year of implementation (academic year of 2021/2022), each team had to select a theme and obtain real databases about the topic from the internet. The team's challenge was the treatment of the data following and combining the different objectives of each subject (Carvalho et al., 2023). In the second year (academic year of 2022/2023), the project had the Climate Changes as a common topic. Each team had to define the subject (for example, forest fires, air quality, and extreme weather events) and to get a dataset available online. In the current year (academic year of 2023/2024), the project has an investigation problem concerning the definition of an efficient supply chain system for an article from an industrial sector in the northern region of Portugal. The team's challenge is to contact a business company to be a partner of the project and to give them access to supply chain data. The aim of this methodology is to give to the second-year students a more holistic and integrated knowledge and understanding of this engineering topic and its relevance to the real world.

In the first two editions, the project teams were formed by students. In the academic year of 2023/2024, 72 students attended IPIEM I and were organised into nine teams of eight students. To develop teamwork skills, this academic year, students faced a new challenge aspect related with the team composition and teamwork, since the teams were formed by a drawing of the member of each team. In this new context, the "natural" groups (i.e. teams formed by the students themselves, eventually according to their friendships) were intentionally discontinued.

IPIEM II assessment includes a poster presentation and discussion (10%), an intermediate report (20%), a final report (40%), and a final presentation and discussion (30%).

2.3 IPIEM III

The most recent edition of IPIEM III CU took place in the second semester of 2022/23, with 69 students divided into seven teams. Following a PBL approach, IPIEM III involved, as PSC, all the remaining CU of the semester, namely Data Analytics (5 ECTS), Decision Models (5 ECTS), Logistics and Supply Chain Management (5 ECTS), Manufacturing Planning and Control (5 ECTS), Project Analysis in Industrial and Engineering Management (5 ECTS). The coordination team was made up of six teachers, one per CU.

The student teams were exposed to an industrial scenario created by the coordination team (based on real contexts), in which a fictitious company faces a considerable increase in demand for three of its product families. Therefore, the company will have to increase its production capacity to be able to respond in a timely manner to new orders, ensuring, in the best possible way, not only the quality of the products, but also low production costs. The general challenge for each student team is to develop proposals / plans at various levels, namely in terms of equipment and labour requirements, logistics, production planning and control and information systems, so that the company's objectives can be achieved.

IPIEM III assessment include two oral presentations, intermediate presentation/discussion (10%) and presentations/discussion (15%), a final report (65%) and the presence on seminars (10%), with invited speakers, about different subjects related to the project.

3 Materials and Methods

The methodology used to analyse transferable skills in the three PBL projects under study (IPIEM I, IPIEM II and IPIEM III) comprised four main steps:

- (1) literature review and selection of transferable skills – it was adopted a framework of 23 transferable skills identified by (Ferraz & Pereira-Guizzo, 2023), due to their relevance to the IEM area, and potential to be developed through PBL projects;
- (2) document analysis – analysis of the material describing each project (e.g. project guide and institutional course catalogue) to identify the transferable skills thought to each project;
- (3) assessment of teachers' perspective – a team for each project held a session to collect their perception on how the respective project promoted the development of the 23 transferable skills. The assessment was made using the scale: (--) not developed; (-) poorly developed; (+) somewhat developed; (++) developed;
- (4) data discussion – the data provided by each coordination team was aggregated and used to identify the most and least developed skills not only in each project, but as a whole, in order to identify weaknesses and strengths.

4 Projects Assessment

4.1 IPIEM I

In addition to the specific skills of the curricular units involved in the IPIEM I, students have the opportunity to develop a set of transferable skills. Through the analysis of the IPIEM I guide, it could be found that the coordination team organised the set of transferable skills into four strands: (1) project management skills, including research capabilities, decision making, organization and time management; (2) personal development skills, namely creativity, critical thinking, self-evaluation and self-regulation; (3) team work, entailing autonomy, initiative, responsibility, leadership, problem solving, interpersonal skills, motivation and conflict management, and (4) communication skills, written and oral.

It can be concluded that there is an alignment between the skills listed in the students' guide, presented in section 4.1, and those proposed by (Ferraz & Pereira-Guizzo, 2023). In the IEM course students learn several techniques related to project management and teamwork that they are expected to explore and practice in the IPIEM I project development. Furthermore, since students need to project a new product and the respective production system, creativity skill, collaboration with the group and assertiveness have been greatly developed. In addition, critical thinking is another skill developed (Alves et al., 2023). The team members must negotiate and achieve consensus on several decisions to be made.

Also, from the deliverables presented in Table 1 (section 2.1), the students develop public speaking skills, as they have three presentations and being assertive during those presentations to argument to teacher's questions. They also develop written communication as they have two reports as deliverables in IPIEM I and, at least, three more brief reports of tasks performed on IEM Degree. Teachers gave them feedback on the first report delivered and on the tasks. In addition, the coordination team used a Padlet where the teams must continuously write the current state of the project during the whole semester.

PBL in IEM has been fundamental to develop such skills as well as social skills as IEM alumni has been testifying (Alves, Leão, et al., 2017; Araujo & Manninen, 2021; Marinho et al., 2021). Nevertheless, a great potential for development exists related to tasks division as the project is complex and the students do not have the skills needed to share the learning between the team members.

4.2 IPIEM II

The project is developed during the semester and the teachers from the four CU provide tutorial support. Apart from the technical skills of the CU that integrate the project, students must acquire transversal skills, as they have to:

- develop an interdisciplinary team project;
- solve multidisciplinary industrial engineering problems involving real data;
- develop teamwork skills in a project environment.

IPIEM II provided a learning environment where students could develop critical thinking, by identifying and solving real-world problems. They learned how to analyse data, make decisions, and work in randomly generated teams. The latter fostered collaboration by requiring students to work effectively in teams with diverse personalities, and drive progress within their teams, reflecting the dynamics of a professional setting. The project also encouraged students to be independent learners and fostered a growth mindset, through preliminary report evaluations in order to turn mistakes into learning opportunities, encouraging a culture of continuous improvement. Furthermore, students were expected to be proactive, and act ethically within diverse teams. On the other hand, time management was enhanced through meeting attendance and deadlines. Finally, both written and verbal communication were developed as well as logical reasoning abilities while presenting/defending their work.

While IPIEM II effectively addressed many transferable skills, students had limited opportunities for developing persistence, adaptability, conflict mediation, active listening, and collaborative solution building. Additionally, encouraging practices such as stimulating collaboration, recognizing contributions, respecting differences, and offering help to colleagues would further enhance the program.

4.3 IPIEM III

Teamwork (with project planning and progress presentations) promotes the development of project management and transferable skills. With regard to the previously mentioned set of transferable skills, the design of IPIEM III aimed to develop the following:

- Autonomous learning – each team should investigate/identify some necessary data and concepts, intentionally missing in the scenario, in order to develop the project;
- Proactivity – students must be proactive by anticipating eventual problems and devising possible countermeasures;
- Openness toward receiving criticism and feedback – during the oral presentations and the development of the tasks, the students receive feedback from the teachers and colleagues;
- Public speaking – two oral presentations (intermediate and final) are mandatory during this project;
- Written communication - at the end of the project each team must write a final report with the integration of all the tasks developed;
- Recognition for contributions – the team develop peer evaluation, just before the two presentations, so members recognize their own work and the contribution of each member of the team;
- Ethics and professionalism – at the beginning of the project, the coordination team develop a schedule for the project with four milestones to promote the accomplishment of the project on time.
- Collective construction of solutions and Collaboration with the group - to promote the teamwork and the development of collective solutions teams with 8 students are created randomly and the collaboration between the team members is also promoted.

During the IPIEM III development, the coordination team promote a few seminaries with professionals about the subjects/areas involved on the project, that are mandatory for all the students. This is an opportunity for the students to interact and learn with professionals from different areas of expertise.

4.4 Results Discussion

This section presents, in table 2, an aggregated perspective of teachers' perceptions about the development of the 23 transferable skills (Ferraz & Pereira-Guizzo, 2023) in the three projects, followed by the corresponding discussion, encompassing problems identification and improvement proposals.

Table 2. Transferable skills identified in each project.

Transferable Skill	Course Unit	IPIEM I	IPIEM II	IPIEM III
Identification of critical points for the work		-	++	+
Expression of creativity		++	+	--
Logical reasoning ability		-	+	+
Persistence		+	-	--
Adaptability		-	-	-
Autonomous learning		+	+	++
Willingness to help colleagues		-	-	+
Proactivity		-	+	+
Attendance		--	+	--
Meeting deadlines		+	++	+
Respect for differences		--	-	++
Collaboration with the group		++	+	+
Ethics and professionalism		--	+	--
Collective construction of solutions		-	-	-
Stimulating collaboration		+	-	+
Recognition for contributions		++	-	++
Written communication		+	++	++
Assertiveness		++	+	++
Active listening		+	-	-
Public speaking		++	++	++
Conflict mediation in the group		-	-	-
Learning based on the recognition of one's own mistake		-	+	-
Openness to receive criticism and feedback		-	+	+

Legend: (++) Developed (+) somewhat developed (-) poorly opportunity to develop (--) Not developed.

By observing Table 2, one can see that public speaking skill stands out across the three projects. With frequent presentations and engagements, students have had several opportunities to refine their communication abilities. These experiences extend beyond the classroom, fostering coherent, confident, and persuasive communicators. Regular feedback further enhances this skill, ensuring continuous improvement and effective communication in both academic and professional contexts. However, amidst the developed skills, certain areas require greater attention. Collective construction of solutions is hindered by a tendency to divide tasks. To address this, integrating team-building exercises and individual assessments covering all subjects within a project can foster a sense of collective responsibility and collaboration. Additionally, conflict mediation within groups lacks effective tools, resulting in unresolved tensions. Implementing workshops focused on conflict resolution techniques and integrating more team-building activities can equip students with practical skills to manage conflicts constructively, fostering a balanced academic environment. In addition, adaptability, attendance, and ethics and professionalism are other critical transferable skills highlighted in Table 2. Adaptability can be developed through exposure to varied tasks and challenges within the projects, encouraging students to quickly adjust to new situations and requirements. Encouraging regular attendance is crucial for instilling discipline and a strong work ethic. This can be achieved through clear expectations and consistent enforcement of attendance policies. Ethics and professionalism can be fostered by including discussions on ethical dilemmas and professional conduct within the curriculum, and by demonstrating these behaviours through faculty and industry mentors.

In conclusion, while public speaking thrives due to regular practice, collective problem-solving and conflict mediation require targeted interventions. By implementing strategies such as team-building exercises, individual assessments, conflict resolution workshops, and emphasizing adaptability, attendance, and ethics and professionalism, educational institutions can foster a wide range of skill sets among students. These efforts prepare them for academic success and future career challenges.

In short, the different IPIEM projects gave students the opportunity to develop various transferable skills that will be valuable to succeed in the workplace.

5 Conclusion

This exploratory study shows the first attempt to concurrently examine the three projects applied throughout the Industrial Engineering and Management Degree at the University of Minho, and it provided valuable insights into the educational process involved. However, it is important to note that this evaluation solely reflects the teachers' perceptions. Thus, the next step involves exploring the students' viewpoints to enrich the analysis and deepen our understanding of PBL dynamics within the educational context. Finally, continuous evaluation and refinement of PBL approaches will allow the teachers' teams to create a more enriching and effective learning environment that fosters both individual and team growth over the three years of the Degree.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia within the R&D Units Project Scope: UIDB/00319/2020.

6 References

- Alves, A. C., Carvalho, J. D., Mesquita, D., Fernandes, S., & Lima, R. M. (2013). IEM@ProjectNetworking: bringing first year students closer to professional practice. *International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education (PAEE2013)*, January, 1–7.
- Alves, A. C., Fernandes, S., Moreira, F., Sá, R. M., Carvalho, D., Sousa, R., Mesquita, D., & Hattum, N. van. (2021). Project-Based Learning: implementação no primeiro ano de um curso de Engenharia. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21814/uminho.ed.26>

- Alves, A. C., Leão, C., Moreira, F., & Teixeira, S. (2017). Project-Based Learning and its Effects on Freshmen Social Skills in an Engineering Program. In M. Otero-Mateo & A. Pastor-Fernandez (Eds.), *Human Capital and Competences in Project Management*. IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.72054>
- Alves, A. C., Leão, C. P., Abreu, M. F., Pimentel, C., Malheiro, M. T., Oliveira, S., Ramos, M. P., & Oliveira, J. M. (2023). Stimulating Critical Thinking Through Report Peer-Review in a Project-Based Learning by Engineering Freshman Students. <https://doi.org/10.1115/IMECE2023-112542>
- Alves, A. C., Moreira, F., Carvalho, M. A., Oliveira, S., Malheiro, M. T., Brito, I., Leão, C. P., & Teixeira, S. (2019). Integrating Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics contents through PBL in an Industrial Engineering and Management first year program. *Production*, 29, e20180111. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0103-6513.20180111>
- Alves, A. C., Moreira, F., Leão, C., & Carvalho, M. (2017). Sustainability and circular economy through PBL: Engineering students' perceptions. In C. Vilarinho, Fernando Castro, & M. de L. Lopes (Eds.), *WASTES – Solutions, Treatments and Opportunities II* (1st ed., p. 462). CRC Press. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1201/9781315206172>
- Alves, A. C., Oliveira, S., Leão, C. P., & Fernandes, S. (2022). IEM@ProjectNetworking revisited: freshmen students closer to professional practice. *International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education*, 12, 182–189. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7057834>
- Araujo, A., & Manninen, H. (2021). Contribution of Project-Based Learning on Social Skills Development (pp. 119–145). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-8816-1.ch006>
- Balalle, H. (2024). Exploring student engagement in technology-based education in relation to gamification, online/distance learning, and other factors: A systematic literature review. *Social Sciences and Humanities Open*, 9(February), 100870. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2024.100870>
- Blinkoff, E., Nesbitt, K. T., Golinkoff, R. M., & Hirsh-Pasek, K. (2023). Investigating the contributions of active, playful learning to student interest and educational outcomes. *Acta Psychologica*, 238(August 2022), 103983. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2023.103983>
- Carvalho, V., Costa, L., Teixeira, S., & Rodrigues, C. S. (2023). A PBL experience with second-year students of Industrial Engineering. *International Conference on Active Learning in Engineering Education*.
- Chatpinyakoo, C., Hallinger, P., & Showanasai, P. (2024). Assessing the effects of online simulation-based learning on skills in managing change for corporate sustainability. *International Journal of Management Education*, 22(2), 100960. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2024.100960>
- Cicmil, S., Williams, T., Thomas, J., & Hodgson, D. (2006). Rethinking Project Management: Researching the actuality of projects. *International Journal of Project Management*, 24(8), 675–686. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2006.08.006>
- Colombo, C. R., Alves, A. C., van Hattum-Janssen, N., & Moreira, F. (2014). Active Learning Based Sustainability Education: a Case Study. *Proceedings of Project Approaches in Engineering Education (PAEE2014)*, September, ID55.1-9. <https://doi.org/10.13140/2.1.1707.1362>
- Colombo, C. R., Moreira, F., & Alves, A. C. (2015). Sustainability Education in PBL Education: the case study of IEM. *Proceedings of the Project Approaches in Engineering Education*, February 2016, 221–228.
- Dunmoye, I. D., Rukangu, A., May, D., & Das, R. P. (2024). An exploratory study of social presence and cognitive engagement association in a collaborative virtual reality learning environment. *Computers & Education: X Reality*, 4(September 2023), 100054. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cexr.2024.100054>
- Fernandes, S., Alves, A. C., & Uebe-Mansur, A. (2021). Student-Centered Assessment Practices (pp. 213–243). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-4769-4.ch009>
- Fernandes, S., Flores, M. A., & Lima, R. M. (2012). Student Assessment in Project Based Learning. In L. C. de Campos, E. A. T. Dirani, A. L. Manrique, & N. van Hattum-Janssen (Eds.), *Project Approaches to Learning in Engineering Education: The Practice of Teamwork* (pp. 147–160). SensePublishers. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-6091-958-9_10
- Ferraz, T., & Pereira-Guizzo, C. (2023). Developing a system for assessing engineering students' transferable skills: evidence for the content validity and replicability of the scales. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 48(4), 667–681. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2023.2195809>
- Kalu, F., Wolsey, C., & Enghiad, P. (2023). Undergraduate nursing students' perceptions of active learning strategies: A focus group study. *Nurse Education Today*, 131(April), 105986. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2023.105986>
- Lima, R. M., Carvalho, D., Assunção Flores, M., & Van Hattum-Janssen, N. (2007). A case study on project led education in engineering: students' and teachers' perceptions. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 32(3), 337–347. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043790701278599>
- Marinho, J. E. T., Freitas, I. R. M., Leão, I. B. dos S., Pacheco, L. O. C. S., Gonçalves, M. P., Castro, M. J. C., Silva, P. D. M., & Moreira, R. J. S. (2021). Project-Based Learning Application in Higher Education (pp. 146–164). <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-8816-1.ch007>
- Marnewick, C. (2023). Student experiences of project-based learning in agile project management education. *Project Leadership and Society*, 4(March), 100096. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plas.2023.100096>
- Moreira, F., Mesquita, D., & Van Hattum-Janssen, N. (2011). The importance of the project theme in Project-Based Learning: a study of student and teacher perceptions. *Proceedings of the Project Approaches in Engineering Education*.
- Navío-Marco, J., Mendieta-Aragón, A., Fernández de Tejada Muñoz, V., & Bautista-Cerro Ruiz, M. J. (2024). Driving students' engagement and satisfaction in blended and online learning universities: Use of learner-generated media in business management subjects. *International Journal of Management Education*, 22(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2024.100963>
- Pinto, A., Oliveira, S., & Carvalho, C. (2023). Do transferable skills matter for engineering students? 5h *International Conference of the Portuguese Society for Engineering Education, CISPEE 2023*, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CISPEE58593.2023.10227618>
- Quibrantar, S. M., & Ezezika, O. (2023). Evaluating student engagement and experiential learning in global classrooms: A qualitative case study. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 78(August 2022), 101290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2023.101290>
- UMinho. (2023). *Industrial Engineering and Management (Bachelor) Study Plan*. https://www.uminho.pt/EN/education/educational-offer/Cursos-Conferentes-a-Grau/_layouts/15/UMinho.PortaUM.UI/Pages/CatalogoCursoDetail.aspx?itemId=4344&catId=13

- Wu, T. T., Sari, N. A. R. M., & Huang, Y. M. (2024). Integrating extended formative assessment in flipped jigsaw learning: Promoting learning engagement and higher-order thinking skills in international business education context. *International Journal of Management Education*, 22(1), 100930. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2024.100930>
- Zen, Z., Reflianto, Syamsuar, & Ariani, F. (2022). Academic achievement: the effect of project-based online learning method and student engagement. *Heliyon*, 8(11). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e11509>
- Zhang, Y., Zhang, X., & Meng, Z. (2024). Effect of interactive immediacy on online learning satisfaction of international students in Chinese universities: The chain mediating role of learning interest and academic engagement. *Acta Psychologica*, 244(97), 104202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2024.104202>